

NORWID IN GREAT BRITAIN

FINAL PROJECT REPORT
LONDON 2021–2023

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INTRODACTION

This final project report outlines the interdisciplinary research undertaken by the Union of Polish Writers Abroad (ZPPnO) and the Polish University Abroad (PUNO) to explore the reception of Cyprian Norwid's works in the GB, particularly within the Polish community in London. The launch of the project in 2021 coincided with the 200th anniversary of the poet's birth and the Norwid Year celebrations in Poland. This helped to integrate the project's activities in London with those in Poland, contributing to the integration of the two communities.

Cyprian Norwid (1821-1883) was a prominent Polish late-Romantic poet, artist and thinker. His time in London was brief (a few months before and after he emigrated to the United States), but it was a significant period in his life that influenced his later work. Although underappreciated during his lifetime, Norwid's writings and artistic contributions have left a lasting legacy.

This project aimed to explore how Norwid's literary and artistic works were received and interpreted by Polish emigrant communities and British audiences. By examining his influence on post-war émigré writers and contemporary cultural practitioners, the study provides valuable insights into the transnational impact of his work. It also explores the continuing relevance of his ideas within contemporary cultural and academic discourse.

The study is particularly relevant today, as it coincides with the bicentenary of Norwid's birth. In a globalised world, cultural exchange and the diasporic experience are increasingly important.

PROJECT OVERVIEW

Principal Investigator and Project Manager	Justyna Gorzkowicz
Principal institutions	Union of Polish Writers Abroad in London (ZPPnO) Polish University Abroad in London (PUNO)
Cooperating	Blue Point Art Gallery London (BPA) Institute of Polish Literature, Faculty of Polish Studies, University of Warsaw (ILP UW)
Members	Grażyna Czubińska (PUNO), Eliza Kącka (UW), Wojciech Klas (PUNO), Adrian Lięża (PUNO), Jarosław Solecki (PUNO/ BPA), Regina Wasiak Taylor (ZPPnO)
Grant	The De Brzezie Lanckoronski Foundation (London, GB, DBLF/2021/22)
Timeline	Mar 1, 2021 to Dec 1, 2023

Understanding Norwid's legacy in GB helps to bridge historical and contemporary cultural dialogues. The project highlights the continuing relevance of Norwid's belief in art's mission to seek truth and awaken conscience, which resonates with current social and artistic movements. It also contributes to wider debates about identity, ethnic minority heritages and the memory of emigrant communities, and provides a basis for comparative studies in these areas.

MAIN GOALS

The primary goal of this interdisciplinary project was to research and analyse the reception of Cyprian Norwid's works in the GB, with a particular focus on the Polish community in London. The project aimed to investigate how Norwid's literary and artistic works were received and interpreted by both the Polish émigré community and the British public, conducting research across a range of disciplines.

A variety of methodologies were employed, such as case studies, archival research, interviews, surveys and mixed-methods qualitative research. The project also integrated digital humanities elements by working with a virtual gallery to exhibit Norwid's sketches. It included educational and social components aimed at educating the public and promoting community engagement through cultural and artistic events.

SCOPE AND ACADEMIC FIELDS

The project spans several academic and cultural fields. It falls within literary studies, including comparative, Polish and Romantic literature. It touches on cultural studies, such as reception and diaspora studies, focusing on the history of Polish exile and migration.

It incorporates aspects of the visual arts and interdisciplinary art studies, and uses digital humanities techniques. It also includes elements of intercultural education, particularly in the context of Polish studies abroad, and memory studies, which examine how cultural and collective memories shape identities and communities.

Additionally, the project activities were linked to the bicentenary celebrations of Norwid's birth, facilitating cultural exchange and collaboration between London and Poland. In achieving these aims, the project aimed to deepen understanding of Norwid's influence and to contribute to wider discussions on ethnic identity, the memory of emigrant communities and comparative cultural studies.

The main activities were carried out in Polish in order to preserve and promote the linguistic legacy as part of the intangible heritage of the minority in the UK. Abstracts and general descriptions of the events were provided in English.

TASKS: Research Panel and Activities: Humanities, Arts and New Media, Didactic Component, Community Engagement (as part of the Scientific Social Responsibility SSR)

CHALLENGES

The project faced significant challenges due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which imposed restrictions and lockdowns in the UK, severely limiting access to research materials and public spaces. As a result, most activities had to be carried out remotely.

Another major challenge was lack of funding. Key support came from a grant from the De Brzezie Lanckoroński Foundation (UK). However, much of the work was done on a voluntary basis and with a smaller contribution of targeted funding. Selected activities were supported by grants received during the project from the Polonia Aid Foundation Trust (PAFT, London), the Norwid Museoin Foundation (Warsaw) and the Polish Embassy in London. These funders are listed next to each achievement.

TASKS OF THE PROJECT

THE MAIN ACTIVITIES WERE DEVELOPED DURING THE REPORTING PERIOD

RESEARCH PANEL: HUMANITIES

- Individual interdisciplinary research in various fields.
- International online conference on the reception of Norwid's work, in collaboration with researchers from outside the project.
- A monograph (in both digital and paper form), incorporating the results of the independent research and conference papers, the book has been peer-reviewed and given a white academic ISBN.

ARTS AND NEW MEDIA

- Cultural and artistic activities, including: research through art, Norwid's work in the context of music and the performing arts.
- Combining literature, digital arts and humanities research: virtual exhibition of Cyprian Norwid's sketches at 3D Gallery (BPA).
- A peer-reviewed book to accompany the exhibition (ISBN series, both digital and print).

DIDACTIC COMPONENT

- A series of short audiovisual documentaries about Norwid in London.
- A series of online meetings with students about Norwid's life and work.

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

- Short piano concert (Chopin)
- Recital inspired by the life and work of Norwid, performed by a Polish theatre group based in London.

OUTCOMES

RESEARCH

The project has produced a number of ground-breaking findings that demonstrate the innovative approaches of the research team. The study of Norwid and urban mythology revealed how the urban environment influenced Norwid's work, adding a new dimension to the understanding of his creativity. Norwid by Stanisław Vincenz provided unique insights into Vincenz's interpretations, enriching the understanding of Norwid's literary contributions. The research on the influence of Norwid on the works of Bolesław Taborski revealed previously unexplored ways in which Norwid's themes and ideas influenced Taborski's literature. Research on the creative works of Norwid in Polish Saturday Schools in Great Britain assessed poet's role in cultural education and heritage preservation among Polish youth, offering new insights. Revisiting Norwid's Work in the Context of Modern Spirituality Studies re-evaluated his writings through the lens of modern spirituality, revealing their contemporary relevance. Finally, precursory publications of Norwid in England documented the earliest publications of his works, tracing his literary presence and reception in the English-speaking world for the first time in such detail.

EDUCATIONAL ENGAGEMENT

Organising online events, including a young students' symposium entitled "Porozmawiajmy o Norwidzie w Londynie" / "Let's Talk About Norwid in London" and "Romantyzm raz jeszcze" / "Romanticism Once Again", in which students explored Norwid's life and works based on the project's research.

CONFERENCE

Organisation of a two-day international academic conference: "Cyprian Norwid: Yesterday and Today. On the Bicentenary of the Birth of the Poet-Emigré", with the participation of representatives of the academic communities of the United Kingdom, the United States, France and scholars from Poland.

EXHIBITION

A virtual exhibition of Norwid's artwork: "Norwid – Sketches" at the Blue Point Art Gallery London, selected from the collection of the National Museum in Krakow, as an element of digital humanities.

SYMPOSIUM

"Wokół książki *Norwid żywy*" / "Around the Book *Norwid Alive*" – a final meeting to summarise the project and promote the monographic book containing the results of the individual researches carried out within the project.

COMMUNITY EVENTS

A poetry and music recital based on Norwid's poetry: "Białe Kwiaty i Czarne" / "White Flowers and Black" performed by the Polish Stage in the UK and Fryderyk Chopin recital by Anna Maria Stańczyk.

AUDIOVISUAL DOCUMENTATION

Producing a series of five short audiovisuals on Norwid in London, in which readers and researchers discuss Norwid's presence in Britain and the reception of his work in exile after the Second World War.

PUBLICATIONS

As part of the project, two multi-author monographic publications were produced: *Norwid żywy – kontynuacja* / *Norwid Alive – Continuation and Pamięć rysunku: szkice plastyczne Cypriana Norwida* / *Memory of Drawing: Sketches by Cyprian Norwid*. Additionally, a series of articles were published in peer-reviewed journals.

WORKFLOW FOR RESEARCH-EXHIBITION "NORWID IN GREAT BRITAIN" PROJECT

"CYPRIAN NORWID: YESTERDAY AND TODAY. ON THE BICENTENARY OF THE BIRTH OF THE POET-EMIGRÉ" – CONFERENCE

CONFERENCE PARTICIPANTS STATISTICS

■ Dr ■ Dr hab. ■ Mgr ■ Prof. dr ■ Prof. dr hab.

Book of Abstracts available in the ZENODO Repository: <https://zenodo.org/records/10606729>

“NORWID – SKETCHES” AT THE BLUE POINT ART GALLERY LONDON

research through art, Digital Humanities

Exhibition archived on the Gallery's website

The poetry and music recital "Białe Kwiaty i Czarne / White Flowers and Black" by Cyprian Norwid was performed by well-known actors from the Polish.UK Stage. This co-production of PUNO, ZPPnO, and POSK was **artistically directed by Helena Kaut-Howson**. The event featured **Zofia Walkiewicz, Konrad Łatacha, Wojtek Piekarski, with music by Daniel Luszczki**.

COMMUNITY EVENTS

scientific social responsibility

Anna Maria Stańczyk, virtual Chopin recital performed by the artist

AUDIOVISUAL DOCUMENTATION

A series of documentary short films following Norwid's footsteps in London, initiated and narrated by ZPPnO President Regina Wasiak-Taylor, in collaboration with the PUNO Institute of European Culture. In addition to researchers of the poet's legacy, London readers and artists inspired by the work of the Romantic poet have been invited to participate in the etude. **The videos are available on the project's YT channel.**

EDUCATIONAL ENGAGEMENT

SYMPOSIUM

The event was the conclusion of a project dedicated to Cyprian Norwid, highlighting his literary and cultural heritage. The meeting discussed various aspects of Norwid's work and his influence on contemporary literature and culture in Poland and the UK. Presentations ranged from the "Norwid in Britain 2021-2023" project to social and educational initiatives inspired by his work. The meeting provided an in-depth analysis and discussion of Norwid's role in today's world, underlining his timeless relevance and impact on contemporary cultural and social challenges.

PUBLICATIONS

The project resulted in two multi-author monographic publications:

- J. Gorzkowicz (ed), *Pamięć rysunku: szkice plastyczne Cypriana Norwida / Memory of Drawing: Sketches by Cyprian Norwid*, London 2021.
- J. Gorzkowicz, E. Kącka, R. Wasiak-Taylor (eds.), *Norwid żywy - kontynuacja / Norwid alive - continuation*, Londyn – Warszawa 2021–2023.
- as well as a series of articles published in a peer-reviewed journal "Pamiętnik Literacki", LXI, LXII, London 2023.

PROJECT MEDIA SUPPORT

The project events were patronised by: International Association of Polish Studies, Federation of Poles in Great Britain, Museion Norwid Foundation, Światowe Stowarzyszenie Mediów Polonijnych, "Londynek.net", "Tydzień Polski".

The main project activities were also regularly announced and documented in the "Polish Studies Newsletter". The journal was among the European digital projects promoted by the European Association for Digital Humanities, which presents research in the digital humanities in Europe.

CONCLUSION

The project dedicated to Cyprian Norwid has influenced the image and reception of the poet, bringing important benefits to literary studies, innovation and society, while maintaining an important link with Polish language and culture in exile.

The project resulted in the publication of two monographs: "Pamięć rysunku: Szkice plastyczne Cypriana Norwida" / "Memory of Drawing: Sketches by Cyprian Norwid" and "Norwid żywy - kontynuacja" / "Norwid Alive - Continuation". These books have provided critical studies and new perspectives on Norwid's life and work, significantly enriching the scholarly discourse on his contributions. In addition, a series of articles published in the peer-reviewed journal "Pamiętnik Literacki" (London) have further disseminated these findings, ensuring a wide academic reach and impact.

An interdisciplinary research approach using methods such as literary analysis, case studies, archival research, interviews, surveys and mixed methods qualitative research provided a comprehensive understanding of Norwid's influence and legacy. The integration of digital humanities, including a virtual gallery of Norwid's sketches and the use of 3D tools, modernised the research approach, making it more engaging and accessible to a wider audience.

The inclusion of artistic activities and new media has greatly enhanced the understanding of Norwid's work. Modern technologies in exhibitions and audiovisual materials allowed for a more immersive and interactive experience. A series of short audiovisual documentaries on Norwid in London, with discussions by readers and scholars, provided an engaging exploration of Norwid's presence in Britain and the reception of his work in exile. Cultural events, such as poetry and music recitals, promoted Polish culture and legacy abroad, celebrating Norwid's work and engaging the community in cultural activities. These events fostered a deeper understanding and appreciation of Polish literature and culture.

By incorporating Norwid's work into educational curricula and public exhibitions, the project has ensured a sustained interest in his work, which will have a long-term impact. This ongoing engagement is crucial for the preservation and appreciation of cultural heritage. The project has bridged historical and contemporary cultural dialogues, highlighting the relevance of Norwid's beliefs and artistic mission in today's world. This has enriched cultural discourse and underlined the lasting impact of Norwid's work on contemporary society.

The Cyprian Norwid project has significantly advanced scholarly research, employed innovative methodologies and promoted community engagement. It has enriched academic scholarship, promoted the appreciation of cultural heritage and maintained a vital link with Polish language and culture in exile, ensuring the celebration and promotion of the intangible heritage of the Polish ethnic minority in the UK.

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About the project in "Polish Studies Newsletter" <https://biuletynpolonistyczny.pl/en/projects/norwid-in-great-britain,1837/details> [06.07.2024].

Project media:

FB: *Norwid w Wielkiej Brytanii*, <https://www.facebook.com/NorwidwLondynie> [06.07.2024].

YT: *Norwid w Wielkiej Brytanii*, <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC-EloH6aGYQFSNrSq12HtJQ> [06.07.2024].